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The dualities of European integration: identity, conflict, and governance in the era of hybrid warfare

by MARCO MARSILI*

1. *Introduction: the importance of the topic and research objectives*

The European Union's resilience is being tested by a new generation of threats that operate in the shadowy realm between war and peace. This article examines the critical interplay between hybrid warfare – encompassing cyberattacks, disinformation, and psychological operations – and the foundational pillars of the European project: its governance models and collective identity. The significance of this research lies in its timing and approach; it seeks to understand how the EU can navigate this complex threat landscape without compromising the democratic values and principles of sovereignty upon which it was built.

Methodologically, this article employs a qualitative and conceptual analysis, drawing on documented case studies of hybrid campaigns (such as the 2014 annexation of Crimea and the 2007 cyber-attacks on Estonia) to dissect their impact on EU cohesion. This empirical focus is complemented by a review of theoretical literature spanning international relations, security studies, and European integration theory. The aim is to bridge the gap between the study of hybrid threats and the normative analysis of EU governance, providing a synthesized perspective on the Union's adaptive capacity.

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This article holds significant importance for several reasons. First, it addresses the evolving complexities of European integration in the context of hybrid threats, which have become a defining feature of the contemporary geopolitical landscape. Hybrid warfare – characterized by its ambiguity and the strategic blending of military and non-military tactics – poses unique challenges to the EU’s governance and stability. Understanding these dynamics is essential for preserving the EU’s core values of democracy, human rights, and the rule of law¹.

By examining the intersection of identity, conflict, and governance, this research seeks to shed light on the EU’s capacity to navigate these multifaceted challenges. Hybrid threats exploit societal divisions, undermine trust in institutions, and destabilize democratic processes. For instance, Russia’s influence strategies in its contested neighborhood illustrate how disinformation and cognitive manipulation can erode social cohesion and political stability². This underscores the need for adaptive measures to counter such threats while safeguarding fundamental freedoms.

Second, the paper situates itself at a critical juncture for the EU. Hybrid conflicts blur traditional distinctions: civilian versus military domains, national versus supranational concerns, and internal versus external security. These blurred lines necessitate a reevaluation of sovereignty within the EU framework, prompting member states to strike a delicate balance between their national interests and the imperative for collective security. As argued, the digital revolution and artificial intelligence (AI) advancements further complicate these dynamics, necessitating innovative gov-

1. Cfr. M. MARSILI, *Hybrid warfare: above or below the threshold of armed conflict?*, in «Honvédségi Szemle – Hungarian Defence Review», vol. 150, n. 1-2, 2022, pp. 37-39.

2. Cfr. M. MARSILI, *The Russian influence strategy in its contested neighbourhood*, in H. MÖLDER, V. SAZONOV, A. CHOCHIA, T. KERIKMÄE (a cura di), *The Russian Federation in the global information warfare. Influence operations in Europe and its neighbourhood*, Springer, Berlin 2021, pp. 149-150, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-49516-4_92021.

ernance models to address both immediate, and systemic challenges³.

This work also explores the transformative potential of redefining sovereignty in the EU. Hybrid threats demand coordinated, cross-border responses that leverage the EU's institutional strength while respecting the autonomy of its member states. The essay posits that adaptive governance – rooted in resilience, institutional flexibility, and ethical standards – is essential for addressing these threats. As noted, the rise of the metaverse and other immersive technologies exemplifies how hybrid warfare evolves, requiring the EU to anticipate and mitigate future risks⁴.

Finally, the contribution integrates insights from interdisciplinary literature on hybrid warfare, human rights, and the nexus of security and sovereignty. By drawing on existing research and exploring innovative pathways, it seeks to contribute to the broader discourse on European integration and security. This involves not only assessing the threats but also identifying opportunities for the EU to emerge stronger. For example, hybrid conflicts can act as catalysts for deeper integration, provided the EU adopts a proactive and unified approach⁵.

Ultimately, this article contends that the EU's success in addressing hybrid threats hinges on redefining integration as a dynamic and adaptive process. This requires a renewed commitment to unity, underpinned by institutional innovation and ethical governance. By fostering resilience and adaptability, the EU can preserve its values and strengthen its role as a global actor in an era of uncertainty.

3. Cfr. M. MARSILI, J. WRÓBLEWSKA-JACHNA, *Digital revolution and artificial intelligence as challenges for today*, in «Media i Społeczeństwo» («Media and Society»), vol. 20, n. 1, 2024, pp. 23-24, <https://doi.org/10.5604/01.3001.0054.6506>.

4. Cfr. M. MARSILI, *Guerre à la carte: Cyber, information, cognitive warfare and the metaverse*, in «Applied Cybersecurity & Internet Governance» (ACIG), vol. 2, n. 1, 2023, pp. 6-7, <https://doi.org/10.60097/ACIG/162861>.

5. Cfr. M. MARSILI, *Hybrid warfare: above or below the threshold of armed conflict?*, cit., pp. 44-45.

2. *The context of European integration*

European integration emerged from the ashes of World War II as a visionary project to ensure lasting peace and stability on a continent ravaged by conflict. This transformative process, initiated with the European Coal and Steel Community (ECSC) and progressively deepened through key treaties like Maastricht and Lisbon, has fundamentally reshaped Europe's political, economic, and social landscape. While designed to foster peace through economic interdependence and shared sovereignty, the integration process has continually navigated a core tension: balancing national interests with the imperative of collective action. This duality has become increasingly critical to understand in the face of 21st-century challenges, notably the rise of hybrid warfare which exploits the very openness and interdependence upon which the EU is built.

The establishment of the European Economic Community (EEC) in 1957 through the *Treaty of Rome*⁶ marked a significant milestone in this endeavor, laying the groundwork for what would later become the European Union (EU) with the *Maastricht Treaty* in 1993⁷. The *Maastricht Treaty* not only formalized the EU but also introduced critical innovations such as the concept of European citizenship and the criteria for economic and monetary union⁸.

The origins of European integration were deeply rooted in the protection of human rights and fundamental freedoms, as emphasized in foundational agreements such as the *European Conven-*

6. Cfr. *Treaty of Rome, Treaty establishing the European Economic Community* (EEC Treaty), signed on 25 March 1957, in force on 1 January 1958. Consolidated versions of the *Treaty on European Union* and the *Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union* (2016/C 202/01) in «Official Journal of the European Union», n. C 202 of 7 June 2016.

7. Cfr. EUROPEAN UNION, *Treaty on European Union (Consolidated Version), Treaty of Maastricht*, 7 February 1992, in «Official Journal of the European Union», n. C 325 of 24 December 2002, pp. 33-184.

8. Cfr. N. NUGENT, *The government and politics of the European Union*, 8th ed., Palgrave Macmillan, London 2017, pp. 114-116, <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-137-454-19-0>.

tion on Human Rights⁹. These principles reflected a shared commitment to democratic governance and the rule of law, which became central tenets of the European project. However, the process was not free from geopolitical complexities. For instance, during World War II, Italian diplomats experienced internal divisions that foreshadowed the broader challenges of post-war European diplomacy. These divisions influenced Italy's role in shaping European integration, particularly in balancing national sovereignty with collective European interests¹⁰.

Over time, European integration has been characterized by a progressive pooling of sovereignty among its member states, allowing for collective decision-making mechanisms and the establishment of common policies in diverse fields, including trade, security, environmental protection, and human rights¹¹. This unique supranational structure has facilitated unprecedented economic prosperity and fostered a sense of shared European identity. Nonetheless, it has also prompted debates about national sovereignty and the democratic legitimacy of EU institutions¹².

The journey of European integration has not been without significant challenges. Economic crises, such as the global financial crisis of 2008 and the subsequent eurozone debt crisis, exposed structural weaknesses in the EU's economic architecture¹³. Additionally, the migration crisis of 2015 tested the EU's capacity for collective action and solidarity, particularly in addressing humanitarian needs while balancing national interests and security

9. Cfr. M. MARSILI, *The protection of human rights and fundamental freedoms at the origins of the European integration process*, in «Europea», vol. 5, n. 1, 2018, pp. 192-193.

10. Cfr. M. MARSILI, *The servant of two masters: Italian diplomats in World War II. Story of a diplomatic civil war and its implications and consequences on post-war foreign policy*, in «Journal of Modern Italian Studies», vol. 27, n. 1, 2022, pp. 21-23, <https://doi.org/10.1080/1354571X.2021.1968497>.

11. Cfr. A. MORAVCSIK, *The choice for Europe: social purpose and state power from Messina to Maastricht*, Cornell University Press, Ithaca, NY 1998, pp. 41-46.

12. Cfr. V.A. SCHMIDT, *Europe's crisis of legitimacy: governing by rules and ruling by numbers in the Eurozone*, Oxford University Press, Oxford 2019, pp. 92-97, <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780198797053.001.0001> Schmidt.

13. Cfr. J.E. STIGLITZ, *The Euro: how a common currency threatens the future of Europe*, W.W. Norton & Company, New York 2016, pp. 45-48.

concerns¹⁴. These events, coupled with the rise of nationalist and populist movements, have amplified tensions within the Union and underscored the need for reform to enhance its resilience and unity.

3. *Definition of hybrid warfare*

Hybrid warfare refers to a complex and multifaceted strategic approach that integrates conventional military force with irregular tactics, cyber warfare, disinformation campaigns, and psychological operations. Unlike traditional warfare, hybrid strategies aim to achieve political objectives by exploiting vulnerabilities in an adversary's social, economic, and political systems without overtly crossing the threshold of formal armed conflict¹⁵. This form of conflict thrives in the “grey zone” between war and peace, leveraging ambiguity and deniability to create confusion and hinder effective responses by targeted states.

The hallmark of hybrid warfare is its adaptability. Actors employing hybrid tactics can seamlessly transition between kinetic and non-kinetic means, exploiting asymmetric advantages. For example, cyberattacks targeting critical infrastructure, misinformation campaigns aimed at polarizing societies, and the use of proxy forces allow aggressors to weaken opponents while maintaining plausible deniability¹⁶.

In the context of the European Union, hybrid warfare poses profound challenges to national and collective security. The interconnectedness of EU member states through shared digital, economic, and political systems makes the bloc particularly susceptible to hybrid threats. Tactics such as cyberattacks on critical infrastructure, the dissemination of fake news on social media

14. Cf. E. GUILD, C. COSTELLO, M. GARLICK, V. MORENO-LAX, *The 2015 refugee crisis in the European Union*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge 2017, pp. 21-26, <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108656715>.

15. Cfr. M. MARSILI, *Hybrid warfare: above or below the threshold of armed conflict?*, cit., pp. 37-39.

16. Cfr. M. MARSILI, *Guerre à la carte: Cyber, information, cognitive warfare and the metaverse*, cit., pp. 3-4.

platforms, and the manipulation of public opinion have the potential to destabilize political systems, undermine democratic processes, and erode public trust in institutions¹⁷.

The Russian annexation of Crimea in 2014 is one of the most studied cases of hybrid warfare. This operation combined conventional military maneuvers with cyberattacks, information warfare, and covert operations by unmarked “little green men”. Russia’s actions in Eastern Europe illustrate the effectiveness of hybrid strategies in achieving strategic goals without provoking direct military retaliation. These events underscore the urgent need for the EU to develop comprehensive strategies to counter such threats, including enhancing cybersecurity, combating disinformation, and fostering resilience among member states¹⁸.

The growing prevalence of hybrid tactics highlights the importance of an integrated approach to security. Hybrid warfare is not limited to state actors; it also involves non-state actors who exploit technological advancements and information asymmetries. As Marsili notes, the emergence of immersive digital platforms, such as the metaverse, adds another layer of complexity to hybrid operations¹⁹. These platforms can be used to conduct sophisticated cognitive operations that manipulate human behavior, further blurring the lines between real and virtual conflicts.

To address these challenges, the EU has taken steps to strengthen its capacity to detect, prevent, and respond to hybrid threats. Initiatives such as the creation of the European Centre of Excellence for Countering Hybrid Threats (Hybrid COE) and the inclusion of hybrid defense measures in the EU Strategic Compass reflect a growing awareness of the need for a coordinated response to this evolving form of conflict²⁰.

17. Cfr. M. MARSILI, J. WRÓBLEWSKA-JACHNA, *Digital revolution and artificial intelligence as challenges for today*, cit., pp. 21-23.

18. Cfr. M. MARSILI, *The Russian influence strategy in its contested neighbourhood*, cit., pp. 152-153.

19. Cfr. M. MARSILI, *Guerre à la carte*, cit., pp. 7-8.

20. Cfr. M. MARSILI, *Hybrid warfare: above or below the threshold of armed conflict?*, cit., p. 46.

4. *Sovereignty and security in the hybrid era: the impact of hybrid warfare on EU identity and governance*

The European Union is a unique political construct where the interplay of identity and governance shapes its policies and responses to contemporary challenges. The concept of identity within the EU is both multilayered and dynamic, encompassing the distinct national identities of its member states alongside a collective European identity. This duality fosters both unity and tension. National identities, deeply rooted in cultural and historical contexts, often clash with the broader notion of European solidarity, especially amidst the resurgence of nationalism in some member states. Scholars like Dinan argue that European identity is not fixed; instead, it evolves in response to internal dynamics and external pressures, such as economic crises, migration, and geopolitical threats²¹.

The EU's efforts to cultivate a shared European identity have historically relied on common values like democracy, human rights, and the rule of law. However, these efforts face challenges, particularly when divisive issues, such as migration or rule of law disputes, exacerbate tensions among member states. As highlighted, these tensions are exploited by external actors through hybrid strategies that aim to deepen divisions within the EU, further complicating the balance between national sovereignty and collective identity²².

This analysis of hybrid threats and EU governance resonates with scholarly work on the contested nature of European identity and resilience. As argued by scholars like Sonia Lucarelli, the EU's ability to project a cohesive identity and respond strategically to external challenges is not merely a matter of policy adjustment but a fundamental test of its political cohesion and nor-

21. Cfr. D. DINAN, *Ever Closer Union: an introduction to European integration*, 4th ed., Lynne Rienner Publishers, Boulder 2010, pp. 23-24.

22. Cfr. M. MARSILI, *The Russian influence strategy in its contested neighbourhood*, cit., pp 154-155.

mative legitimacy²³. The hybrid warfare paradigm, therefore, forces a re-examination of core EU theories, challenging the Union to reconcile its supranational aspirations with the realities of a fragmented geopolitical landscape.

This challenge to the EU's political cohesion resonates with the research of Sonia Lucarelli, who argues that the Union's identity and its external policy are inextricably linked, and that crises often serve as critical junctures where the EU's normative legitimacy and internal solidarity are fundamentally contested and defined. The hybrid warfare paradigm, by exploiting internal divisions, acts as precisely such a stress test, forcing a re-examination of the EU's ability to uphold its foundational values while under attack²⁴.

This interplay between identity and external pressure is reflected in the EU's unique governance structure, which is characterized by a hybrid blend that blends intergovernmental and supranational elements. Institutions like the European Commission (EC), the European Parliament (EP), and the Council of the European Union operate within a multi-level governance framework. This structure enables diverse stakeholders to participate in decision-making processes but also creates challenges in achieving consensus, particularly during crises²⁵. For example, the EU's response to the COVID-19 pandemic exposed gaps in coordination and solidarity, prompting debates about the need for more centralized authority versus respect for national autonomy.

Hybrid warfare adds a layer of complexity to the EU's governance and identity. Defined as the strategic use of conventional and unconventional tactics, including cyber warfare, disinformation, and irregular operations, hybrid threats exploit vulnera-

23. Cfr. S. LUCARELLI, *European political identity, foreign policy and the others' image: An under-explored relationship*, in F. CERUTTI, S. LUCARELLI (eds.), *The Search for a European Identity: Values, Policies and Legitimacy of the European Union*, Routledge, London 2008, pp. 23-42.

24. Cfr. *ivi*.

25. Cfr. I. BACHE, S. GEORGE, S. BULMER, *Politics in the European Union*, 4th ed., Oxford University Press, Oxford 2017, pp. 38-40.

bilities in open, democratic societies²⁶. The Russian annexation of Crimea in 2014 is a quintessential example, showcasing the integration of military aggression with cyberattacks and propaganda to achieve political objectives while avoiding outright war²⁷.

The EU has made strides in addressing hybrid threats, recognizing their potential to undermine its institutional integrity and member state cohesion. Initiatives like the *European Cybersecurity Strategy* and the establishment of the Hybrid COE reflect efforts to enhance resilience against cyber and informational threats²⁸. However, the effectiveness of these measures depends on the ability of member states to align national security strategies with collective EU goals, a task often complicated by divergent priorities and resource disparities.

The intersection of sovereignty and security in the hybrid era presents profound challenges for the EU. Hybrid warfare blurs traditional distinctions between civilian and military domains, internal and external security, and national versus collective interests. This ambiguity necessitates a reevaluation of the EU's governance models to address these evolving threats effectively. The *Common Security and Defence Policy* (CSDP) exemplifies efforts to enhance cooperation among member states, yet its success is often hampered by conflicting national priorities²⁹.

The concept of sovereignty itself is being redefined within the EU framework. Marsili and Wróblewska-Jachna argue that sovereignty in the digital age must encompass not only territorial integrity but also the protection of informational and cognitive domains from hybrid manipulation³⁰. This perspective aligns with the EU's growing focus on cyber sovereignty and the regulation

26. Cfr. M. MARSILI, *Hybrid warfare: above or below the threshold of armed conflict?*, cit., pp. 38-40.

27. Cfr. M. GALEOTTI, *Hybrid war or gibridnaya voina? Getting Russia's non-linear military challenge right*, Lulu.com, 2016.

28. Cfr. L. KELLO, *The virtual weapon and international order*, Yale University Press, New Haven 2017, pp. 49-51.

29. Cfr. F.G. HOFFMAN, *Conflict in the 21st century: the rise of hybrid wars*, Potomac Institute for Policy Studies, Arlington 2007, https://www.potomacinstitute.org/images/stories/publications/potomac_hybridwar0108.pdf.

30. Cfr. M. MARSILI, J. WRÓBLEWSKA-JACHNA, *op. cit.*, pp. 21-22.

of digital platforms to counter disinformation and protect democratic processes.

Addressing hybrid threats requires the EU to adopt a more resilient and adaptive approach to integration. Governance models must emphasize institutional flexibility, enabling rapid and coordinated responses to crises. As Marsili notes, emerging technologies like AI and the metaverse introduce new dimensions to hybrid warfare, necessitating forward-looking strategies that anticipate and mitigate risks³¹.

Equally important is the cultivation of a robust European identity that can withstand the pressures of internal divisions and external manipulation. This involves not only reaffirming shared values but also engaging citizens in a participatory governance process that builds trust and inclusivity. Efforts to promote media literacy, enhance digital citizenship, and strengthen the EU's strategic communication capabilities are critical in this regard³².

The EU stands at a crossroads where identity, governance, and security converge in the face of hybrid threats. By redefining integration as a dynamic and adaptive process, the EU can strengthen its resilience and maintain its unity amidst geopolitical uncertainties. This requires a renewed commitment to institutional innovation, ethical governance, and a shared vision for the future of Europe. As the EU navigates these challenges, it has the opportunity to emerge as a more cohesive and influential global actor, safeguarding its values and ensuring the well-being of its citizens.

5. The historical context of European integration

The historical context of European integration is deeply intertwined with the desire for lasting peace and stability in the aftermath of World War II. Europe, devastated by years of conflict, faced an urgent need for cooperation to rebuild its economies, prevent future hostilities, and foster a sense of shared destiny.

31. Cfr. M. MARSILI, *Guerre à la carte*, cit., pp. 8-9.

32. Cfr. M. MARSILI, *The Russian influence strategy in its contested neighbourhood*, cit., pp 169-170.

The war underscored the dangers of nationalism and economic rivalry, motivating European leaders to create frameworks that would bind their nations together in pursuit of common goals. The foundational moment of this effort was the creation of the European Coal and Steel Community (ECSC) in 1951, an innovative initiative designed to regulate these critical industries, which had previously been at the heart of conflict. By promoting economic interdependence and cooperation, the ECSC aimed to make war not only undesirable but materially impossible. This initiative served as a steppingstone for deeper integration, proving that collaboration in one sector could foster trust and create a model for broader unification³³.

The momentum of integration grew with the signing of the *Treaty of Rome* in 1957, which established the European Economic Community. This treaty was a bold expansion of the integration project, envisioning a common market and customs union that would facilitate the free movement of goods, services, capital, and people. The governance of this emerging union marked a shift from purely intergovernmental cooperation, where decisions required unanimity, to a supranational approach characterized by shared institutions with binding decision-making powers. This structural evolution was crucial in addressing the complexities of a diverse and growing membership, as it allowed for more efficient coordination and the gradual pooling of sovereignty in key policy areas. Scholars have noted that this period laid the foundation for the EU's later achievements, demonstrating the potential for collective action to overcome economic and political fragmentation³⁴.

Over subsequent decades, a series of transformative treaties further defined the trajectory of European integration. The *Maastricht Treaty* of 1992 was a landmark development, formally establishing the European Union and introducing the concept of European citizenship. It also laid the groundwork for the Economic and Monetary Union (EMU) and the eventual adoption of

33. Cfr. D. DINAN, *Ever Closer Union*, cit.

34. Cfr. I. BACHE, S. GEORGE, S. BULMER, *op. cit.*

the euro as a common currency. This treaty represented a significant deepening of political integration, reflecting the aspirations of European leaders to build a cohesive and competitive bloc capable of wielding global influence. However, it also reignited debates over the balance of power between national governments and EU institutions, as member states had to cede certain powers in exchange for the perceived benefits of unity. The question of sovereignty became a recurring theme, with some critics viewing the EU as a threat to national autonomy, while proponents argued that collective governance was essential for addressing transnational challenges³⁵.

The *Lisbon Treaty*, which came into force in 2009, represented another milestone in the evolution of EU governance³⁶. Designed to streamline decision-making processes and enhance the union's global presence, the treaty introduced significant reforms, such as the creation of a permanent President of the European Council and an expanded role for the European Parliament. These changes sought to address institutional inefficiencies and improve the EU's ability to respond to crises, including the Eurozone debt crisis and the migration crisis, which exposed weaknesses in its existing frameworks. However, the *Lisbon Treaty* also underscored the persistent tensions between the desire for deeper integration and the need to respect national sovereignty. This duality remains a defining feature of the EU, influencing debates on issues ranging from fiscal policy to border management and foreign affairs³⁷.

Throughout its history, European integration has been shaped by the interplay between national interests and the collective ambition of building a unified Europe. Each step in the process – from the ECSC to the treaties of Maastricht and Lisbon – has re-

35. Cfr. F. SCHIMMELFENNIG, *European integration (theory and practice): revisiting the 'ever closer union'*, in «Journal of European Public Policy», vol. 25, n. 6, 2018, pp. 843-853.

36. Cfr. EUROPEAN UNION, *Treaty of Lisbon amending the Treaty on European Union and the Treaty establishing the European Community*, 13 December 2007, in «Official Journal of the European Union», n. C306/01 of 31 December 2007, pp. 1-271.

37. Cfr. T.G. MAHNKEN (ed.), *Competitive strategies for the 21st century: theory, history, and practice*, Stanford University Press, Redwood City 2012.

flected the challenges and opportunities inherent in balancing sovereignty with the need for cooperation. The EU's governance structures have evolved in response to changing political, economic, and social realities, demonstrating both resilience and adaptability. Understanding this historical context is essential for analyzing the EU's contemporary challenges, as the lessons of the past continue to inform its efforts to navigate an increasingly complex geopolitical landscape. The integration process, while imperfect, has transformed Europe, fostering peace and prosperity while setting a precedent for regional cooperation that resonates far beyond its borders. As the EU faces new crises and debates its future direction, the historical foundations of integration provide a vital lens for evaluating its achievements and charting its path forward.

This historical narrative also illustrates the EU's unique capacity for innovation in governance and adaptation to shifting paradigms. The union has consistently proven its ability to transform challenges into opportunities, leveraging crises to deepen integration and refine its institutional frameworks. For instance, the Eurozone crisis prompted significant reforms in economic governance, including the creation of the European Stability Mechanism and stronger fiscal oversight mechanisms. Similarly, the migration crisis of the mid-2010s forced the EU to reexamine its policies on asylum and border management, leading to new initiatives like the reinforcement of the European Border and Coast Guard Agency (FRONTEX). Each crisis has underscored the EU's duality as both a project of idealistic unification and a pragmatic response to the practical demands of governance in an interconnected world.

The EU's historical evolution also reflects the broader ideological tensions that have shaped modern Europe. On one hand, the integration process represents a triumph of multilateralism, emphasizing cooperation, shared values, and collective action. On the other hand, it has consistently faced resistance from nationalist movements and Euroscepticism, which argue for the primacy of state sovereignty and criticize the perceived overreach of EU institutions. These opposing forces have created a dynamic

and often contentious political environment, where integration is both celebrated as a source of stability and innovation and questioned as a potential threat to cultural and political autonomy.

Furthermore, the EU's historical trajectory has been shaped by its external environment, including its relationships with global powers like the United States, Russia, and China. The Cold War, for example, provided a geopolitical backdrop that encouraged Western European countries to align more closely, both economically and politically, as a bulwark against Soviet influence. More recently, the rise of hybrid threats, globalization, and the digital revolution have introduced new dimensions to the challenges faced by the EU, requiring continuous innovation in its policy frameworks. These external pressures have often served as catalysts for deeper integration, reinforcing the union's commitment to collective security, economic interdependence, and global competitiveness.

In short, the historical context of European integration reveals a story of resilience, adaptability, and ambition. From the ashes of World War II to the complex challenges of the 21st century, the EU has evolved into a unique political entity that defies traditional definitions of statehood and sovereignty. Its governance structures, shaped by decades of treaties and reforms, reflect an ongoing effort to balance national interests with the imperatives of collective action. As the EU continues to navigate an uncertain future, the lessons of its past provide invaluable insights into its potential pathways forward. By understanding the historical forces that have shaped European integration, scholars, policymakers, and citizens alike can better appreciate the union's achievements and the challenges that lie ahead.

6. Hybrid warfare: an overview

Hybrid warfare has evolved into a critical concept in contemporary security discourse, particularly as nations and organizations confront new and unpredictable threats. Unlike traditional warfare, which primarily involves direct military confrontation

between states, hybrid warfare combines conventional military tactics with a variety of unconventional methods such as irregular warfare, cyber operations, economic pressure, and information manipulation. This multifaceted strategy enables both state and non-state actors to exploit vulnerabilities in their adversaries while maintaining strategic ambiguity, complicating traditional forms of deterrence and response³⁸. Consequently, hybrid warfare has become a primary concern for policymakers, especially within the European context, where geopolitical tensions and regional instabilities have underscored the need for novel security approaches.

The defining characteristics of hybrid warfare are its flexibility and reliance on a diverse set of tools to achieve strategic objectives. These tools range from irregular military tactics, such as insurgencies and proxy forces, to non-military operations, including cyber-attacks, economic coercion, and information manipulation. A significant aspect of hybrid warfare is its capacity to target societal divisions within the adversary state, exploiting fractures based on political, ethnic, or cultural lines. This manipulation often manifests as disinformation campaigns aimed at confusing, misleading, and dividing the population, thereby weakening the legitimacy of the state and sowing discord among its people. The combination of these tactics enables aggressors to destabilize their targets without resorting to full-scale war, thus avoiding the direct risks associated with conventional military conflict³⁹.

In Europe, the rise of hybrid warfare has been clearly demonstrated by Russia's actions, particularly in its interventions in Ukraine and the Baltic states. The annexation of Crimea in 2014 serves as a key example of hybrid warfare in action. In this operation, Russia deployed a combination of conventional military force, covert operations, and local proxy groups, while simultaneously launching an intense disinformation campaign aimed at

38. Cfr. P. POMERANTSEV, *Nothing is true and everything is possible: the surreal heart of the new Russia*, PublicAffairs, New York 2014.

39. Cfr. L. KELLO, *op. cit.*

justifying its actions and manipulating public perception, both domestically and internationally. This strategy of ambiguous warfare allowed Russia to achieve its objectives while avoiding direct confrontation with NATO forces, highlighting the asymmetrical nature of hybrid warfare and its ability to exploit the vulnerabilities of modern democracies⁴⁰. Similarly, the 2007 cyber-attacks on Estonia underscored the vulnerabilities of European nations to hybrid threats. Coordinated cyber assaults targeted Estonian government and private sector institutions, disrupting critical services and eroding public trust in the state's ability to protect its citizens and infrastructure. This attack, while not involving traditional military means, demonstrated how hybrid tactics could destabilize a nation's political system and undermine its national security⁴¹.

The impact of hybrid warfare on both national and EU security is profound and far-reaching. Hybrid threats blur the lines between war and peace, complicating the determination of appropriate responses. Often, hybrid warfare does not present an immediate, overt military threat but operates in the gray zone between peace and war, where conventional military responses may seem inappropriate or ineffective. This ambiguity complicates decision-making for governments and institutions, leading to delayed or indecisive responses that leave targets vulnerable to further exploitation. Additionally, the non-traditional nature of hybrid warfare means that traditional military forces, designed for conventional conflicts, may be ill-equipped to counter these types of threats. This gap in defense capabilities necessitates a rethinking of security strategies and the development of new tools to address hybrid tactics effectively⁴².

40. Cfr. M. GALEOTTI, *Hybrid war or gibrinaya voina?*, cit.; F.G. HOFFMAN, *Conflict in the 21st century*, cit.

41. Cfr. P. POMERANTSEV, *op. cit.*

42. Cfr. EUROPEAN COMMISSION, *EU Security Union Strategy*, https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/promoting-our-european-way-life/european-security-union_en; EUROPEAN COMMISSION, *Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on the EU Security*

In response to these challenges, the EU has recognized the urgent need for a more coordinated and comprehensive approach to security and defense. The establishment of the European Defence Fund aims to promote collaboration among EU member states in developing defense technologies and capabilities, reflecting a growing recognition of the need for collective action. The EU has also focused on strengthening its cyber resilience, acknowledging the increasing significance of cybersecurity in countering hybrid threats. Cyber-attacks, as demonstrated in the case of Estonia, can disrupt critical infrastructure, undermine public confidence, and destabilize governments, all central objectives in hybrid warfare. Furthermore, the EU has sought to enhance cooperation with NATO, recognizing that the challenges posed by hybrid warfare are often transnational and require a unified, multilateral response. However, these efforts must balance the competing interests of national sovereignty and collective security. While member states increasingly recognize the necessity of cooperation in the face of hybrid threats, ongoing tensions remain regarding the extent to which national interests should be subordinated to collective EU actions, particularly in defense and intelligence sharing⁴³.

The *Joint Framework on Countering Hybrid Threats* highlights the necessity of a coordinated approach that bridges intelligence gaps and accelerates response times, thereby mitigating the impact of such threats⁴⁴. As Europe continues to confront the evolving challenges of hybrid warfare, it is clear that a robust and

Union Strategy, COM/2020/605 final, 24 July 2020, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0605>.

43. Cfr. M. GALEOTTI, *Hybrid war or gibridnaya voina?*, cit.; F.G. HOFFMAN, *Conflict in the 21st century*, cit.

44. Cfr. EUROPEAN COMMISSION, *Joint Communication to the European Parliament and the Council. Joint Framework on Countering Hybrid Threats: A European Union Response*, 6 April 2016, JOIN/2016/018 final, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52016JC0018>; EUROPEAN COMMISSION, HIGH REPRESENTATIVE OF THE UNION FOR FOREIGN AFFAIRS AND SECURITY POLICY, *Joint Communication to the European Parliament, the European Council and the Council. Increasing Resilience and Bolstering Capabilities to Address Hybrid Threats*, 13 June 2018, JOIN (2018) 16 final, https://www.ecas.europa.eu/sites/default/files/joint_communication_increasing_resilience_and_bolstering_capabilities_to_address_hybrid_threats.pdf.

adaptive governance framework is essential. Traditional notions of state sovereignty are being tested by the increasing interdependence of nations and the transnational nature of hybrid threats. To counter these threats effectively, the EU must continue to strengthen its internal cohesion, enhance its military and cyber capabilities, and foster deeper cooperation among its member states. At the same time, it must ensure that its response mechanisms remain flexible and adaptable, as hybrid warfare tactics continue to evolve in response to changing geopolitical dynamics.

Ultimately, hybrid warfare represents a significant and growing challenge to both national and EU security. By blending conventional and unconventional methods, it exploits the vulnerabilities of modern democracies and creates ambiguity that complicates traditional military responses. The EU's efforts to address hybrid threats reflect a broader recognition of the need for enhanced cooperation, both within Europe and with global partners. As the nature of conflict continues to evolve, the EU's ability to adapt its governance structures and security policies will be essential in safeguarding its stability and ensuring the protection of its member states from the full spectrum of hybrid warfare tactics.

7. Identity in the Context of Hybrid Warfare

The concept of identity plays a crucial role in shaping political, social, and cultural dynamics, particularly within the European context. This is especially pertinent when considering hybrid warfare, a modern form of conflict that aims to undermine political cohesion and identity by exploiting divisions and vulnerabilities. In the case of the European Union, the concept of identity is central to the ongoing process of integration, fostering cooperation among member states and building a sense of shared belonging based on common values and cultural heritage. However, hybrid warfare tactics, with their capacity to exploit these divisions, pose significant threats to the stability of this collective

identity, threatening the EU's foundational principles of trust and solidarity.

European identity has evolved from the continent's shared historical experiences, notably the aftermath of World War II. The devastation caused by the war created a collective desire for peace, stability, and cooperation that transcended national borders. According to scholars like Dinan, this history has fostered a sense of belonging among European citizens, which has been integral to the development of a shared European identity⁴⁵. The EU has actively worked to reinforce this identity through various programs and policies designed to increase intercultural understanding and encourage cooperation. One of the most significant of these initiatives is the ERASMUS program, which promotes cultural exchange and solidarity among young Europeans. This initiative has been instrumental in shaping a European identity that values diversity and encourages cross-border cooperation.

However, the emergence of hybrid threats in recent years has raised serious concerns about the integrity of European identity. Hybrid warfare, with its combination of conventional and unconventional methods, including disinformation and cyber operations, directly targets the unity and cohesion of societies. The ambiguity inherent in hybrid threats allows them to exploit societal vulnerabilities, particularly by exacerbating existing political, cultural, and social divisions. Disinformation campaigns, for example, can be used to manipulate public opinion, sow discord, and deepen mistrust between European nations. These tactics are particularly effective in undermining the shared European identity by playing on historical, political, and cultural divides within the EU⁴⁶. In many cases, these hybrid tactics aim to destabilize the European project itself by eroding the trust that member states have in each other, thus undermining solidarity.

The impact of hybrid threats on European identity is evident in how these tactics exploit and amplify existing societal divi-

45. Cfr. D. DINAN, *Ever Closer Union*, cit.

46. Cfr. E. REICHBORN-KJENNERUD, P. CULLEN, *What Is hybrid warfare?*, Policy Brief 1/2016, Norwegian Institute of International Affairs (NUPI), Oslo 2016, <http://hdl.handle.net/11250/2380867>.

sions. Kello points out that hybrid warfare frequently targets areas of societal fault lines, such as nationalism, regionalism, and cultural identity, in order to create division⁴⁷. In this way, hybrid warfare seeks to weaken the political unity that has characterized the EU. Disinformation campaigns, for instance, can amplify nationalist sentiments, which can lead to a resurgence of populism and the rejection of EU values. Countries such as Hungary and Poland have become focal points for these hybrid tactics, where governments have used these methods to consolidate power and challenge the EU's norms and expectations. A European Parliamentary Research Service report notes that these challenges to European values are often linked to the exploitation of political and societal divisions, a hallmark of hybrid warfare strategies aimed at undermining unity within the EU⁴⁸.

Case studies of identity conflicts within the EU further illustrate the disruptive potential of hybrid warfare on both national and collective European identities. The situation in Ukraine is a particularly significant example. The conflict in Ukraine, particularly following the annexation of Crimea by Russia in 2014, has highlighted the vulnerabilities of countries caught between competing national identities and allegiances. Ukraine's aspirations to join the European Union have been complicated by the geopolitical dynamics in the region, particularly Russia's use of hybrid warfare tactics, including disinformation, cyberattacks, and the support of local proxies. These tactics have not only destabilized the Ukrainian state but have also raised profound questions about the identity of Eastern European nations in relation to the EU. As Ukraine navigates its complex relationship with both Russia and the EU, hybrid warfare plays a pivotal role in shaping its national identity and political alignment⁴⁹.

In addition to external threats, hybrid warfare has also contributed to the rise of populist movements within the EU. These

47. Cfr. L. KELLO, *op. cit.*

48. Cfr. P. PAWLAK, *Understanding hybrid threats*, PE 564.355, European Parliamentary Research Service (EPRS), 22 June 2015, [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/think-tank/en/document/EPRS_ATA\(2015\)564355](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/think-tank/en/document/EPRS_ATA(2015)564355).

49. Cfr. F.G. HOFFMAN, *Hybrid warfare and challenges*, cit.

movements, which often draw on fears and insecurities exacerbated by hybrid threats, position themselves against perceived external or internal enemies, including immigrants, political elites, and EU regulations. These movements frequently frame their narratives around a return to national identity, often using populist rhetoric that targets the EU's legitimacy. One of the most significant manifestations of this trend was the Brexit referendum in the United Kingdom, where hybrid tactics, including misinformation campaigns and emotional appeals to national identity, played a crucial role in shaping the public's perception of the EU. The use of hybrid methods to sway public opinion highlights how identity can be manipulated to serve political agendas, often at the expense of unity and cooperation. The Brexit referendum, as Dinan notes, not only reshaped the UK's relationship with the EU but also raised serious questions about the future of European identity itself, particularly in the face of growing Euroscepticism and populism⁵⁰.

In closing, the relationship between identity and hybrid warfare presents profound challenges for the EU. Hybrid threats continue to evolve and exploit existing divisions, targeting the core of European identity and the unity it has fostered among member states. As these threats grow in sophistication, they pose a significant risk to the stability and integrity of the EU. Addressing the challenges posed by hybrid warfare requires a multifaceted approach that includes reinforcing a shared European identity while countering the divisive tactics used to undermine it. The EU must respond to these threats by fostering resilience and solidarity among its member states, ensuring that its foundational values of unity, cooperation, and peace prevail in the face of hybrid challenges. Only through collective action and cooperation can the EU hope to safeguard the cohesion that has been essential to its success and overcome the challenges posed by hybrid warfare.

By strengthening internal cohesion, promoting shared values, and reinforcing collective security, the European Union can effectively combat hybrid threats and preserve its identity as a united

50. Cfr. D. DINAN, *Ever Closer Union*, cit.

and resilient political entity. While the hybrid nature of contemporary conflicts complicates this task, the EU's commitment to promoting democracy, rule of law, and human rights provides a solid foundation for overcoming these challenges. Addressing the impact of hybrid warfare on European identity is not only a matter of protecting sovereignty and national interests but also safeguarding the ideals that have defined the European project from its inception.

Through enhanced cooperation, the EU can mitigate the disruptive effects of hybrid threats by developing robust strategies for countering disinformation, improving cyber resilience, and promoting greater societal cohesion. Additionally, EU institutions must work to ensure that member states remain united in their response to these threats, despite the political and social divides that hybrid tactics aim to exploit. Only by cultivating a stronger, more resilient European identity – one that is less susceptible to manipulation and division – can the EU ensure its continued success in the face of evolving challenges.

As the geopolitical landscape continues to shift and hybrid warfare becomes more prevalent, the EU must adapt and evolve. The need for a shared European identity that transcends national boundaries and political divisions has never been more urgent. In this context, strengthening the EU's collective response to hybrid threats will not only safeguard its security but also ensure the continued relevance and stability of European integration in the 21st century.

8. *Governance challenges in the era of hybrid warfare*

The emergence of hybrid warfare has posed significant governance challenges for the European Union and its member states. Hybrid threats, which combine conventional military force with irregular warfare, cyber operations, disinformation campaigns, and other non-traditional tactics, have complicated the EU's traditional security paradigms. As these threats evolve, the EU must adapt its institutional response to ensure both national and collective security, while also safeguarding the demo-

cratic values and ethical principles that form the foundation of the European project⁵¹. The growing complexity of hybrid warfare, often involving multiple actors and blurred lines between state and non-state actions, has made it increasingly difficult for the EU to maintain a cohesive and effective defense posture.

One of the most important aspects of the EU's response to hybrid threats has been its institutional evolution. As the nature of threats became more multifaceted, the EU recognized the necessity for a more integrated approach to security, emphasizing cooperation, coordination, and resilience across its member states. The establishment of the European Centre of Excellence for Countering Hybrid Threats in 2017, for example, was a pivotal development in this regard. This center provides a collaborative platform for member states to share intelligence, best practices, and develop joint strategies for countering hybrid threats, which range from cyberattacks to influence operations and economic coercion⁵². Its work highlights the EU's commitment to improving security governance in the face of growing hybrid threats.

Moreover, in recent years, the EU has implemented a variety of programs aimed at strengthening the cyber resilience of its member states. These initiatives include the EU *Cybersecurity Act*⁵³, which seeks to harmonize cybersecurity efforts across the Union, and the development of the EU's *Strategic Compass for Security and Defence*⁵⁴, which emphasizes the need for greater

51. Cfr. K. GILES, *Russia's 'new' tools for confronting the West: continuity and innovation in Moscow's exercise of power*, Royal Institute of International Affairs, London 2016, <https://www.chathamhouse.org/sites/default/files/publications/2016-03-russia-new-tools-giles.pdf>; cfr. T.G. MAHNKEN, *Competitive strategies for the 21st century*, cit.

52. Cfr. EUROPEAN COMMISSION, *EU Security Union Strategy*, cit.

53. Cfr. EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, COUNCIL OF THE EUROPEAN UNION, *Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) N. 526/2013 (Cybersecurity Act)* (Text with EEA relevance), PE/86/2018/REV/1, in «Official Journal of the European Union», n. L 151 of 7 June 2019, pp. 15-69.

54. EUROPEAN EXTERNAL ACTION SERVICE (EEAS), *A Strategic Compass for Security and Defence. For a European Union that protects its citizens, values and interests and contributes to international peace and security, from the Council of the European Union*, 21 March 2022, https://www.eeas.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/strategic_compass_en3_web.pdf.

military and civilian cooperation in dealing with hybrid challenges⁵⁵. Despite these efforts, the ongoing challenge lies in ensuring that national security priorities do not undermine the broader goals of collective security within the EU framework. Member states, particularly those with historically different security needs or political orientations, can sometimes prioritize national approaches over EU-wide solutions, creating friction and delays in response to hybrid threats⁵⁶.

Furthermore, the rise of populism and nationalism within several EU member states presents a unique challenge. These movements, which often promote national sovereignty and question the legitimacy of EU institutions, can complicate efforts to foster solidarity and common action in the face of hybrid threats. Populist rhetoric, which tends to frame security and defense issues in nationalistic terms, can undermine the EU's collective response to hybrid warfare by pitting individual state interests against the greater good of EU-wide security cooperation⁵⁷. As such, managing domestic political pressures while maintaining EU unity in the face of external hybrid threats requires careful diplomatic and public communication efforts, focusing on the importance of solidarity and mutual security.

Ethical governance also remains a central issue in the EU's hybrid warfare strategy. The use of disinformation campaigns, cyberattacks, and other unconventional tactics by state and non-state actors raises critical ethical concerns. The blurred nature of hybrid warfare complicates the ability to hold perpetrators accountable under traditional legal frameworks. In many cases, it is difficult to determine whether an action constitutes an act of war or a covert operation designed to influence public opinion and disrupt societal cohesion⁵⁸. As noted by Kello, hybrid threats often operate in a "gray zone," where actions are not clearly de-

55. Cfr. EUROPEAN COMMISSION, *EU Security Union Strategy*, cit.

56. Cfr. D. DINAN, *Europe recast: a history of European Union*, Palgrave Macmillan, London 2017.

57. Cfr. F. SCHIMMELFENNIG, *The politics of European Union enlargement: theoretical and comparative perspectives*, 1st. ed., Routledge, London 2009.

58. Cfr. K. GILES, *op. cit.*; MAHNKEN, *op. cit.*

fined under international law⁵⁹. This lack of clarity presents significant challenges for policymakers attempting to balance effective defense with respect for international law and human rights.

The manipulation of public opinion through disinformation campaigns remains one of the most direct threats to the EU's democratic processes. These campaigns, often state-sponsored or supported by non-state actors, aim to erode trust in institutions, sow division among citizens, and undermine the legitimacy of democratic governance. The ongoing challenge of countering disinformation highlights the need for the EU to not only strengthen its security response but also invest in enhancing the resilience of its citizens to such threats. According to Galeotti, the EU must foster media literacy, encourage critical thinking, and promote transparency in order to combat the influence of disinformation and empower citizens to participate more actively in the democratic process⁶⁰. This includes ensuring that the digital public sphere remains a space for open, honest debate, rather than one dominated by polarized narratives and fake news.

In response to these challenges, the EU has also worked to develop its strategic communication capabilities, aiming to improve its ability to counter disinformation and offer a cohesive narrative in the face of hybrid threats. The EU's East STRATCOM Task Force (ESCTF or ESTF), created in 2015, serves as a key component of these efforts, specifically focusing on countering Russian disinformation campaigns⁶¹. The effectiveness of these efforts, however, is often hindered by the rapid spread of disinformation via social media platforms, which can quickly reach millions of people, creating a cycle of misinformation that is difficult to break. Thus, the EU's response to hybrid warfare must not only be institutional but also societal, requiring a shift toward greater media literacy, stronger online accountability, and enhanced cybersecurity measures.

59. Cfr. L. KELLO, *op. cit.*

60. Cfr. M. GALEOTTI, *Russian political war: moving beyond the hybrid*, Routledge, London 2019.

61. Cfr. EUROPEAN COMMISSION, *EU Security Union Strategy*, cit.

Lastly, it is essential to address the broader implications of hybrid warfare for EU governance. Hybrid threats do not only target military or political institutions; they also have the potential to undermine societal trust and cohesion. The increasing use of cyberattacks to disrupt critical infrastructure, influence elections, and steal sensitive information shows how hybrid tactics are employed not only to achieve political goals but also to weaken public confidence in governmental systems⁶². This, in turn, poses a serious challenge to the EU's social fabric, which relies on public trust in democratic institutions. The EU must, therefore, not only focus on military and intelligence responses to hybrid threats but also invest in building resilient societies that can withstand the social and psychological effects of disinformation and cyberattacks.

In short, the governance challenges posed by hybrid warfare require a comprehensive and adaptive response from the EU and its member states. By reinforcing its institutional capacity, enhancing cooperation, and focusing on ethical governance, the EU can strengthen its ability to counter hybrid threats effectively. The ongoing evolution of these threats requires a proactive, collaborative approach, ensuring that the EU remains resilient in an increasingly complex security environment.

9. *Case Studies*

The analysis of specific hybrid warfare incidents affecting the European Union provides valuable insights into the complexities of contemporary security challenges. These case studies not only highlight the nature of hybrid threats but also illustrate the responses from EU institutions and member states, as well as the lessons learned and best practices that can be derived from these experiences. As hybrid warfare tactics evolve, so too must the EU's ability to adapt and respond effectively to safeguard its collective security, democratic values, and unity.

62. Cfr. K. GILES, *op. cit.*; cfr. T.G. MAHNKEN, *op. cit.*

One of the most significant examples of hybrid warfare in Europe is the Russian annexation of Crimea in 2014. This incident exemplifies the use of hybrid tactics, where Russia combined conventional military force with irregular warfare, cyber operations, and disinformation campaigns to achieve its objectives. The rapid deployment of unmarked troops, often referred to as “little green men”, alongside a sophisticated information warfare strategy aimed at justifying the annexation, showcased the effectiveness of hybrid tactics in undermining the sovereignty of Ukraine⁶³. The disinformation campaigns surrounding the annexation further complicated the situation, as Russia manipulated narratives to create a sense of legitimacy for its actions, while portraying the EU and its member states as weak and divided. This multifaceted approach demonstrated the challenge of countering hybrid threats, where the conventional military component is only one part of a broader strategy of influence.

The EU’s response to the Crimean crisis was multifaceted, involving economic sanctions against Russia, diplomatic efforts to support Ukraine, and the enhancement of security cooperation among member states. The imposition of sanctions marked a significant shift in the EU’s approach to external aggression, demonstrating a willingness to use economic tools to counter hybrid threats⁶⁴. However, the EU’s internal divisions and the challenges of coordinating a unified response among all member states highlighted the difficulty of achieving collective action in the face of hybrid warfare.

Another pertinent case study is the cyber-attack on Estonia in 2007, which serves as a critical example of how hybrid warfare can disrupt national security and public trust. The attack, which targeted government websites, banks, and media outlets, was attributed to Russian hackers and was seen as a response to Estonia’s decision to relocate a Soviet-era war memorial. This incident highlighted the vulnerabilities of digital infrastructure and

63. Cfr. P. POMERANTSEV, *op. cit.*

64. Cfr. F.G. HOFFMAN, *Hybrid warfare and challenges*, in «Joint Force Quarterly», vol. 52, 2009.

the potential for cyber operations to create chaos and undermine societal cohesion⁶⁵. The attack's impact on Estonia's security was not limited to the immediate disruption of services but also included long-term effects on public trust in the government and the perceived integrity of the nation's digital infrastructure.

In response, Estonia took significant steps to bolster its cyber defenses, becoming a leader in cybersecurity within the EU. The establishment of the NATO Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence (CCDCOE) in Tallinn further exemplifies the collaborative efforts to enhance resilience against hybrid threats⁶⁶. Estonia's experience underscores the necessity of strengthening cyber resilience, as the digital domain increasingly becomes a central battleground in hybrid warfare. Moreover, the country's proactive measures in the wake of the attack have become a model for EU member states seeking to improve their own cybersecurity frameworks, illustrating the need for a unified approach to address the growing threat of cyber warfare within the EU.

The lessons learned from these case studies underscore the importance of a coordinated and comprehensive response to hybrid warfare. The EU's institutional framework has evolved to address these challenges, with initiatives aimed at improving information sharing, enhancing cyber resilience, and fostering cooperation among member states. The establishment of the Hybrid COE in 2017 is a testament to this commitment, providing a platform for member states to collaborate on strategies to counter hybrid tactics⁶⁷. This center plays a crucial role in promoting the exchange of best practices and developing tailored responses to hybrid threats, helping the EU to remain agile and adaptive in the face of evolving security risks.

Moreover, these case studies reveal the necessity of balancing national interests with collective security. While individual mem-

65. Cfr. L. KELLO, *op. cit.*

66. Cfr. K. GILES, *op. cit.*

67. Cfr. EUROPEAN COMMISSION, *Joint Communication to the European Parliament and the Council. The EU's Cybersecurity Strategy for the Digital Decade*, JOIN/2020/18 final, 16 December 2020, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:52020JC0018>.

ber states may prioritize their own security concerns, the interconnected nature of hybrid threats necessitates a unified approach. The rise of populist movements within the EU, which often advocate for nationalistic policies, poses additional challenges to achieving this balance. As noted, the legitimacy of collective action can be undermined by domestic political pressures, making it essential for the EU to engage in effective communication and public diplomacy to reinforce the importance of solidarity in the face of hybrid threats⁶⁸. These populist movements, often fueled by disinformation and the manipulation of societal divisions, further complicate efforts to build a cohesive and coordinated response to hybrid warfare.

To sum up, the analysis of hybrid warfare incidents affecting the EU highlights the complexities of contemporary security challenges and the need for adaptive governance. The responses from EU institutions and member states demonstrate a growing recognition of the importance of collaboration and resilience in countering hybrid threats. By learning from these case studies and implementing best practices, the EU can enhance its capacity to navigate the evolving landscape of hybrid warfare and safeguard its collective security. The ability to balance national interests with collective security, strengthen cyber defenses, and foster public trust in democratic institutions will be key to ensuring that the EU remains resilient in the face of future hybrid challenges.

10. *Pathways to resilience and adaptability: long-term strategies for enhancing EU governance and fostering a cohesive European identity*

In the face of evolving hybrid threats, the European Union must adopt pathways to resilience and adaptability that enhance its governance structures, foster a cohesive European identity, and consider the long-term implications for EU integration. The EU's

68. Cfr. A.L.P. PIRRO, P. TAGGART, S. VAN KESSEL, *The populist politics of Euroscepticism in times of crisis: a framework for analysis*, in «Politics», vol. 38, n. 3, 2018, pp. 253-262.

awareness of these challenges is reflected in its most recent strategic initiatives. The ongoing Readiness 2030 debate (formerly ReArm Europe) and the proposals within the *White Paper on European Defence* signal a growing recognition that resilience requires not just reactive measures but a proactive, future-proofed investment in defence capabilities, technological sovereignty, and a streamlined decision-making process that can operate at the speed of hybrid threats⁶⁹.

To enhance its governance in the context of hybrid warfare, the EU must prioritize the development of a comprehensive and coordinated approach to security. This involves strengthening existing institutions and creating new frameworks that facilitate collaboration among member states. One key strategy is the establishment of a robust intelligence-sharing mechanism that allows for real-time information exchange regarding hybrid threats. Effective intelligence sharing is crucial for enhancing situational awareness and enabling timely responses to emerging threats⁷⁰.

Moreover, the EU should invest in capacity-building initiatives that enhance the resilience of member states against hybrid threats. This includes providing resources and training to improve cybersecurity measures, counter-disinformation campaigns, and strengthen critical infrastructure. The establishment of the European Cybersecurity Agency (ENISA), as proposed in the EU's Cybersecurity Strategy, could play a pivotal role in coordinating efforts to bolster cyber defenses across member states⁷¹.

69. Cfr. EUROPEAN COMMISSION, *White Paper for European Defence – Readiness 2030*, March 2025, https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/e6d5db69-e0ab-4bec-9dc0-3867b4373019_en.

70. Cfr. EUROPEAN UNION AGENCY FOR CYBERSECURITY (ENISA), *Threat Landscape 2020*, ENISA, Chalandri, 27 October 2021, <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/enisa-threat-landscape-2021>; ENISA, *Cross-Sector Exercise Requirements*, ENISA, Chalandri, March 2022, <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/cross-sector-exercise-requirements>.

71. Cfr. EUROPEAN COMMISSION, *Joint Communication to the European Parliament, the Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. Cybersecurity Strategy of the European Union: An Open, Safe and Secure Cyberspace*, JOIN (2013) 1 final, 7 February 2013, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52013JC0001>.

Additionally, the EU must enhance its crisis management capabilities by integrating civil and military responses to hybrid threats. The European External Action Service (EEAS) has already begun to develop a more comprehensive approach to security that includes both military and civilian tools, which is essential for addressing the multifaceted nature of hybrid warfare⁷².

Fostering a cohesive European identity is essential for enhancing the EU's resilience against hybrid warfare. A strong sense of shared identity can counteract the divisive narratives propagated by hybrid tactics, which often seek to exploit societal divisions and undermine trust in democratic institutions. To cultivate this identity, the EU must prioritize initiatives that promote cultural exchange, education, and civic engagement among its citizens.

Programs such as ERASMUS+, which facilitates student exchanges and educational opportunities across Europe, play a vital role in fostering a sense of belonging among young Europeans. By encouraging cross-cultural interactions and shared experiences, these initiatives can help to build a more cohesive European identity that transcends national boundaries⁷³. Additionally, the EU should invest in public awareness campaigns that highlight the benefits of European integration and the shared values that unite member states, such as democracy, human rights, and the rule of law.

Furthermore, engaging citizens in the democratic process is crucial for reinforcing a cohesive European identity. The EU must prioritize transparency and inclusiveness in its decision-making processes, ensuring that citizens feel their voices are heard and valued. Initiatives such as the Conference on the Future of Europe (April 2021-May 2022), which aims to involve citizens in discussions about the EU's future, can serve as a platform for fos-

72. Cfr. EUROPEAN EXTERNAL ACTION SERVICE (EEAS), *Countering Hybrid Threats*, March 2024, <https://www.eeas.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/2024/2024-countering-Hybrid-Threats.pdf>.

73. Cfr. D. DINAN, *Ever Closer Union*, cit.

tering a sense of ownership and collective responsibility among Europeans⁷⁴.

The pathways to resilience and adaptability have significant long-term implications for EU integration. As the EU navigates the complexities of hybrid warfare, it must consider how its governance structures and identity can evolve to meet future challenges. The need for a more integrated approach to security may necessitate a reevaluation of the balance between national sovereignty and collective action. Member states must recognize that hybrid threats are transnational in nature and require coordinated responses that transcend national borders.

This shift towards greater integration could lead to the establishment of a more unified European defense policy, enabling member states to pool resources and capabilities in addressing hybrid threats. A collective defense framework that includes both military and non-military dimensions could enhance the EU's overall security posture and resilience⁷⁵. However, achieving this level of integration will require overcoming political and ideological barriers, particularly in an era marked by rising nationalism and populism.

Moreover, the long-term implications for EU integration extend beyond security considerations. The challenges posed by hybrid warfare may catalyze a renewed commitment to the core values of the EU, reinforcing the importance of democracy, rule of law, and human rights. As the EU confronts external threats, it has an opportunity to reaffirm its identity as a values-based union, promoting these principles both internally and externally. This commitment to shared values can serve as a unifying force, fostering solidarity among member states and enhancing the EU's global standing as a champion of democracy and human rights.

Finally, the pathways to resilience and adaptability in the face of hybrid warfare require a multifaceted approach that enhances EU governance, fosters a cohesive European identity, and consid-

74. Cfr. EUROPEAN COMMISSION, *Conference on the future of Europe*, https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/new-push-european-democracy/conference-future-europe_en.

75. Cfr. T.G. MAHNKEN, *Competitive strategies for the 21st century*, cit.

ers the long-term implications for integration. By prioritizing collaboration, capacity-building, and citizen engagement, the EU can strengthen its ability to respond to hybrid threats while reinforcing the values that underpin its existence. As the EU navigates this complex landscape, it must remain committed to unity and cooperation, ensuring that it emerges stronger and more resilient in the face of evolving challenges.

11. *Conclusion*

The exploration of hybrid warfare and its implications for the European Union has revealed several critical insights. First, hybrid threats, characterized by the blending of conventional and unconventional tactics, pose significant challenges to the security and stability of the EU. The case studies of incidents such as the Russian annexation of Crimea and the cyber-attack on Estonia illustrate the multifaceted nature of these threats, which can undermine national sovereignty, disrupt societal cohesion, and exploit vulnerabilities in democratic institutions.

Second, the EU's response to hybrid threats has evolved, highlighting the necessity for a comprehensive and coordinated approach to security governance. Strategies such as enhancing intelligence sharing, investing in cybersecurity, and fostering collaboration among member states are essential for building resilience against hybrid tactics. Furthermore, the importance of fostering a cohesive European identity cannot be overstated, as it serves as a countermeasure to the divisive narratives propagated by hybrid warfare. Looking ahead, the future of European integration will be significantly influenced by the ongoing challenges posed by hybrid threats. The need for a more integrated approach to security may catalyze deeper cooperation among member states, leading to the establishment of a unified European defense policy. This shift could enhance the EU's overall security posture, enabling member states to pool resources and capabilities in addressing hybrid threats effectively.

However, achieving this level of integration will require overcoming political and ideological barriers, particularly in an era

marked by rising nationalism and populism. The EU must navigate these challenges while reinforcing its commitment to shared values, such as democracy, human rights, and the rule of law. The ongoing dialogue fostered by initiatives like the Conference on the Future of Europe presents an opportunity for citizens to engage in shaping the EU's trajectory, ensuring that the Union remains responsive to the needs and aspirations of its people.

In conclusion, the importance of unity and ethical governance in the face of hybrid threats cannot be overstated. As the EU confronts these complex challenges, it must remain steadfast in its commitment to collaboration and solidarity among member states. A united Europe, grounded in shared values and ethical governance, is better equipped to respond to the multifaceted nature of hybrid warfare.

Moreover, the EU's ability to uphold its democratic principles and promote a cohesive European identity will be crucial in countering the divisive tactics employed by hybrid threats. By fostering a culture of resilience, transparency, and inclusivity, the EU can strengthen its capacity to navigate the evolving landscape of security challenges while reinforcing the values that underpin its existence.

In practical terms, this analysis suggests that for the EU to navigate the hybrid threat landscape effectively, policymakers must prioritize three actionable areas: 1) Investing in Predictive Capabilities: Enhancing intelligence-sharing and early-warning systems within agencies like ENISA and the Hybrid COE to anticipate rather than just react to threats. 2) Hardening Democratic Resilience: Formalizing media literacy and strategic communication programs into the core of civic education across member states to inoculate the public sphere against disinformation. 3) Streamlining Decision-Making: Revisiting mechanisms within the CFSP and CSDP to allow for more agile and decisive collective action in the "grey zone", potentially through qualified majority voting on certain security matters. Without such concrete, institutionalized steps, the EU's declaratory commitment to resilience risks remaining just that.

Il dualismo dell'integrazione europea: identità, conflitto e governance nell'era della guerra ibrida

Abstract

L'articolo esamina le crescenti complessità del processo d'integrazione europea rispetto alle minacce ibride, in particolare le tattiche non convenzionali come la guerra cyber, la disinformazione e la manipolazione psicologica, che minano la coesione politica, sociale ed economica in Europa. Queste sfide testano la capacità dell'UE di unire gli stati membri sotto strategie di sicurezza coese che preservano gli impegni etici e legali custoditi nei trattati e nelle carte dell'UE. Il paper esplora, dunque, come l'UE può rafforzare i suoi modelli di governance per rispondere alle minacce ibride e, al contempo, salvaguardare i diritti fondamentali dei cittadini degli stati membri, nonché le strade attraverso cui l'UE può rafforzare la resilienza e l'adattabilità. Infine, l'articolo sostiene che il successo dell'UE in un'era di minacce ibride risiede nel ridefinire l'integrazione come un processo flessibile.

This article examines the evolving complexities of European integration in the face of hybrid threats, particularly non-conventional tactics like cyber warfare, disinformation, and psychological manipulation, which undermine political, social, and economic cohesion across the EU. These challenges test the EU's ability to unify member states under cohesive security strategies that preserve ethical and legal commitments enshrined in EU charters and treaties. The paper explores how the EU can strengthen its governance models to respond to hybrid threats while safeguarding the fundamental rights of citizens across all member states, and the pathways through which the EU can enhance resilience and adaptability. Ultimately, this article contends that the EU's success in an era of hybrid threats relies on redefining integration as an adaptive process.

Parole chiave: Unione europea, Russia, Disinformazione, Sicurezza, Stabilità.

Keywords: European Union, Russia, Disinformation, Security, Stability.